

IR58025A/IR21567. But the last two hybrids also possess long slender and attractive grains, moderate HR, and a high VER, a good combination of quality traits. ■

Studying comparative suitability of CMS lines

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Parental lines constitute the first and foremost step in a hybrid breeding program. In this context, developing a commercially viable cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) line is considered to be a highly cumbersome process. In fact, the belated success of hybrid rice technology in India was basically due to the nonavailability of a CMS line suited to the tropics. Over the years, a large number of male sterile lines with different cyto sterility sources have been developed in India and elsewhere. Only a few—such as IR58025A and IR62829A—are now used commercially in India. They possess all the essential traits—complete and stable male sterility, high outcrossing rate, better grain quality, easy restorability, good combining ability, and adaptability—of a commercially viable CMS line. Some 64 CMS lines from India, China, Malaysia, and IRRI were evaluated along with IR58025A, IR62829A, and standard checks in the wet season of 1995 and 1996 and dry season of 1994 and 1995 to assess their comparative suitability for commercial use. The CMS lines, along with their corresponding maintainers, were grown for maintenance and evaluation for their floral traits such as pollen sterility, panicle and stigma exertion, outcrossing rate, duration and angle of glume opening, growth duration, number of effective tillers, spikelets panicle⁻¹, grain type, adaptability, and pigmentation (if any). Each CMS line was characterized for all the traits individually. The final value was

obtained by adding together the weighted score allotted to a CMS line for all these traits. This single final value on a 1 to 9 scale indicated the line's practical utility.

Only 11 lines were found to be equally better for all the characters studied than IR58025A and IR62829A: four CMS lines (IR68280A, IR68897A, IR68899A, and IR69628A) from IRRI, two (DRR2A and DRR3A) from the Directorate of Rice Research, and one each from China (9601A), Malaysia (MH-841A), IARI (Pusa 5A), Cuttack (CRMS 31A), and Faizabad (NDCMS 7A). Some of the promising CMS lines were IR67684A, IR68890A, IR68902A, IR68279A, IR68895A, and CRMS 6A. About 31 lines possess one or two good characters and can be used for specific purposes. All Chinese lines, for example, are useful as cyto sterility sources to convert promising maintainers into new CMS lines. The remaining 16 lines have one or more drawbacks and will need further improvement. The promising CMS lines are now being studied for their combining ability and use in breeding programs. ■

Identifying a new long-duration CMS line (APMS 5A) for coastal regions

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Several male sterile lines developed in India belong to the early- to medium-duration group. Hybrids developed using these male sterile lines are also of early to medium growth duration. These hybrids are not suitable for cultivation during the wet season, particularly in the coastal areas of Andhra Pradesh, where long-duration varieties are predominantly grown. We need to develop long-duration rice hybrids to increase rice productivity and fit them into the cropping system. An effort was made to develop long-duration (145-150 d) and stable local

cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines. Several testcrosses were made using local long-duration elite lines and IRRI CMS lines to screen the elite varieties for their maintaining or restoring ability. A few long-duration maintainer lines were identified based on pollen and spikelet sterility. MTU4870 was therefore selected and successfully converted into a local cyto sterile line in the background of a wild abortive source of cytoplasm through the backcross breeding technique. This line was designated as APMS5A.

APMS5A is a long-duration (145-150 d) line with tolerance for brown planthopper, bacterial leaf blight, rice tungro virus, and sheath blight. It also possesses a sturdy culm. It has a comparable angle of spikelet opening duration (190 min), angle of spikelet opening (31°C), stigma exertion, and natural outcrossing potential (12%) with the popular CMS line IR58025A. APMS5A, a 100% sterile line, is the first long-duration CMS line developed in India with desirable floral and agronomic traits. A few effective restorers were also identified. APMS5A will facilitate the development of long-duration rice hybrids suitable for cultivation in the coastal areas. ■

Wide hybridization for diversification of CMS in rice

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To identify new sources of male sterility-inducing cytoplasm within the A genome of genus *Oryza*, 132 inter-specific crosses involving accessions of four wild (*O. rufipogon*, *O. nivara*, *O. barthii*, and *O. longistaminata*) and two cultivated species (*O. sativa* and *O. glaberrima*) were effected. Accessions possessing sterility-inducing cytoplasm were identified following reciprocal and F₂ backcross methods and advanced through substitution backcrossing to develop cytoplasmic